

"Data Archives/Services and Research Community"

NESSTAR

Preparing, viewing, analyzing, downloading

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The old dream

- All existing empirical data on-line
- An integrated resource discovery gateway to identify and locate these data
- Extensive amounts of metadata available
- The ability to carry out simple on-line browsing, visualization and analysis
- The ability to seamlessly subset and download data and metadata to specialized analysis or visualization tools
- Efficient hyperlinks from data sources to relevant papers and notes.

S. Musgrave / P. Littlewood (cca. 2000)

Some data about Nesstar usage

Nesstar is currently run **by most archives in Europe**, and a reasonable number of data libraries in US/Canada.

Nesstar was originally **developed by and for archives**, and is designed to fit many important documentation and dissemination use-cases for data archives. Nesstar was also the first tool to **support DDI**, which is still a highly relevant standard for data documentation.

There are currently > **130 instances of Nesstar Server worldwide**, from Vancouver to Taiwan and from South-Africa to Iceland.

In volume, the **International Household Survey Network** (<http://ihsn.org/home/>) is the most important Nesstar user. IHSN do not use Nesstar Server, but they use Nesstar Publisher as a documentation tool for statistical agencies in a large number of (developing) countries on all continents.

Nesstar also fully supports **multilingual metadata**, which makes it possible to document data in more than one language (without duplicating data).

Nesstar Server comes **with a set of APIs** that allow for third-party integration with data, metadata and functionality (e.g. tabulation and download operations) on the server.

Because of the APIs and the DDI support, the Nesstar platform is also very easy to repurpose for other services, e.g. the **CESSDA Portal** and the **DwB Data Discovery portal**.

Important/high profile users of Nesstar include:

[European Social Survey](#):

[UK Data Service](#)

[GESIS ZACAT](#)

It also supports aggregate data (cubes).
[Norway's Institute of Public Health](#)

EUROPEAN ELECTION DATABASE

Nesstar Publisher (*Located on desktop*)

Nesstar Publisher – a sophisticated authoring environment that can publish data from a variety of sources (including SPSS, SAS, Excel etc.). The tool includes a specialised metadata editor, data and metadata validation routines and metadata templates that provide standardisation and control.

Easy editing/creation and export of DDI documented datasets with XML experience needed.	Tools to compute/recode/label new, or existing, variables to be added to a dataset before publishing.
Tools to validate metadata and variables.	The ability to import and export data to the most common statistical formats, including delimited files.
The ability to include automatically generated frequency and summary statistics for each variable.	Multilingual - Arabic, Chinese, English, French, Russian and Spanish

Nesstar Publisher

Projects:

- My Projects
 - studkr12-primer izpolnjene template
 - hrr11_p1_v1_r1-full
 - rspStatment

Naslov

Ljudska prava u svijesti građana/ki Bosne i Hercegovine

Podnaslov

Variables

Number	Name	Label	Width	StartCol	EndCol	Record	Decimals
v1	m	Godina istraživanja	8	*	*	*	0
v2	m_1	Identifikacioni broj	4	*	*	*	0
v3	m_6	Region	1	*	*	*	0
v4	m_7	Tip naselja	1	*	*	*	0
v5	p_1	Ljudska prava	1	*	*	*	0
v6	p_2	Kako se šтите ljudska pra	1	*	*	*	0
v7	p_3_1	Koja ljudska prava vam p	3	*	*	*	0
v8	p_3_2	Koja ljudska prava vam p	3	*	*	*	0
v9	p_3_3	Koja ljudska prava vam p	3	*	*	*	0
v10	p_4_1	Pravo na život	2	*	*	*	0
v11	p_4_2	Pravo na slobodu i bezbj	2	*	*	*	0
v12	p_4_3	Pravo na jednakost pred	2	*	*	*	0
v13	p_4_4	Pravo na rad, izbor zapo	2	*	*	*	0
v14	p_4_5	Pravo na slobodu izražav	2	*	*	*	0
v15	p_4_6	Pravo na socijalno osigui	2	*	*	*	0

- Category Hierarchy
 - 1 - najvažnije
 - 2 - 2
 - 3 - 3
 - 4 - 4
 - 5 - 5
 - 6 - 6
 - 7 - najmanje važno

Value: Label:

Category Text:

Level Name:

GeoMap URI:

Documentation

- Statistics
- Weights
- Documentation

- VarDoc
 - Pre-Question Text
 - Literal Question
 - Post-Question Text
 - Interviewer Instructions
 - Notes

Pre-Question Text

Literal Question

4.5 Rangirajte po važnosti 1 (najvažnije) 7 (najmanje važno) navedena ljudska prava po značaju: pravo na slobodu izražavanja, misli i vjeroispovjesti

Variable information

Data Type:

Numeric

Measure:

Nominal

Is Time Variable

Is Weight Variable

Min: Max: Decimals:

1 7 0

Implicit decimals

Missing data:

= 0

*

Nesstar Server (*Located on server*)

Nesstar Server - includes an SQL-based metadata management system, a data storage system, a powerful statistical engine as well as a flexible access control system.

Nesstar WebView – totally customisable and configurable layer that presents the search, browse, display, analysis and retrieval options to the user. Able to seamlessly handle survey data, cubes and other resources.

Multiple crosstabulation and recoding

Regression and correlation analysis

Please select a data format from the drop-down box.
If you wish to download a subset of the data, click on the 'Subset' button.
Click on 'Download' to start downloading.
Please note that you may be asked for a password.

- USDAS
 - Ljudska prava u svijesti građana/ki Bosne i Hercegovine
 - Metadata
 - Study Description
 - Bibliographic Citation
 - Study Scope
 - Methodology
 - Data Access
 - Other Study
 - Other Document
 - Variable Descriptions
 - Variable
 - Demografske v
 - Ostalo

Depositor

Name	Affiliation	Abbreviation
Centar za ljudska prava	Univerzitet u Sarajevu	HRC

Dataset: Ljudska prava u svijesti građana/ki Bosne i Hercegovine
 Istraživanje javnog mnijenja o stanju ljudskih prava u Bosni i Hercegovini za 2011 godinu

Variable p_4_2: Pravo na slobodu i bezbjednost

LITERAL QUESTION

4.2 Rangirajte po važnosti 1 (najvažnije) 7 (najmanje važno) navedena ljudska prava po značaju: pravo na slobodu i bezbjednost

Values	Categories	N	
1	najvažnije	58	5.9%
2	2	543	55.4%
3	3	156	15.9%
4	4	107	10.9%
5	5	47	4.8%
6	6	43	4.4%
7	najmanje važno	26	2.7%
0		16	

SUMMARY STATISTICS

Valid cases	980
Missing cases	16
Minimum	1.0
Maximum	7.0
This variable is numeric	

Dataset: Ljudska prava u svijesti građana/ki Bosne i Hercegovine

Istraživanje javnog mnijenja o stanju ljudskih prava u Bosni i Hercegovini za 2011 godinu

Pravo na slobodu i bezbjednost: Categories Pol: Categories Type: Column percentage

Pol	Muškarci	Žene	Total
Pravo na slobodu i bezbjednost			
najvažnije	5.2	6.7	5.9
2	53.1	57.7	55.4
3	16.9	14.9	15.9
4	12.0	9.9	10.9
5	5.0		
6	4.8		
najmanje važno	3.1		
Total	100.0	100.0	
N=	484		

Export to Excel, PDF
Bookmark page

Dataset: Ljudska prava u svijesti građana/ki Bosne i Hercegovine

Istraživanje javnog mnijenja o stanju ljudskih prava u Bosni i Hercegovini za 2011 godinu

Pravo na slobodu ...i vjeroispovjesti: Categories

Frequency
0 25 50 75 100 125 150 175 200 225 250 275 300

STUDIES DUBLIN CORE

Advanced Search

Search criteria:

Study Description contains

Search for: datasets variables tables

Search catalogs:

- USDAS
- USDAS-EN

SEARCH

Pravo na slobodu

6
najmanje važno

% of all
0.0 2.5 5.0 7.5 10.0 12.5 15.0 17.5 20.0 22.5 25.0 27.5 30.0

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Thank you for your attention!

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